

Reflectance

Editors: Casey Jenson & Alison K. Post

Studying Arctic Ice
(Credit: NASA Image of the Day/Kathryn Hansen)

Quick Updates

- Interim Earth Lab Director and Research Scientist, Virginia Iglesias, was quoted in a New York Times article "[What Are the Largest Wildfires in U.S. History?](#)"
- Earth Lab Research Scientist, Nayani Ilangakoon led a presentation for over 175 high school students at the American Heart Association STEM Event for Girls.
- Earth Lab/ESIIL Interim Analytics Hub Director, Cibele Amaral, led a workshop in Brazil to discuss a collaborative research agenda for biodiversity and climate change with Brazilian scientists.
- ESIIL Director, Jennifer Balch, published an article in Nature's [News and Views](#) about the increasing risk of nighttime fires.
- In collaboration with faculty from Anthropology, Earth Lab was awarded a \$14,000 seed grant through CU Boulder's Institute of Behavioral Science to study the impacts of increased wildfires on archeological sites.
- Research Scientist Matt Rossi published a two-part series in the Journal of Geophysical Research – Earth Surface, titled "Stochastic in Space and Time". Check out Parts [1](#) & [2](#).

Casey to Cal-Wood: Intro to Forests & Fires

Several Earth Lab researchers teamed up with CU Science Discovery to explore wildfire impacts on forest ecosystems with the eager minds of the future. This engaging two-day event, held on March 5th and 6th, welcomed approximately 135 eighth graders from Casey Middle School (Boulder) into the heart of the Cal-Wood area, a region touched by the Cal-Wood wildfire in 2020.

The experience was crafted to guide these young explorers through tree identification and the use of drones and satellite imagery to assess fire damage and the subsequent recovery of forest systems.

By Nayani Ilangakoon

Students use binoculars to observe the treetops and fire damage. Photos by Nayani Ilangakoon.

Earth Data Science Education

The [Environmental Data Science Innovation & Inclusion Lab](#) (ESIIIL) launched its first [Earth Data Science Short Course](#), with over 80 registered participants! This is the first in a series of four, 4-week-long virtual courses that will introduce Earth Data Science (EDS) educators and leaders to fundamental EDS education tools. Sign up next spring for course #2!

Registration has opened for Earth Lab's [Earth Data Analytics Professional Graduate Certificate](#). This 9-credit program is designed to provide students with a powerful combination of skills in earth science, data analytics, interdisciplinary collaboration, and science communication. Apply now through **August 9th**.

Launch your
career in
earth data
science!

Graduate Student Accomplishments

This spring, two Earth Lab graduate students successfully defended their Masters/PhD. Nathan Korinek presented his Masters thesis titled "Does Fire Beget Fire? An Investigation of Fire's Influence on Future Fire Severity in Western US Forests," and Dr. Brendan Hobart presented his PhD dissertation titled "From snails to sagebrush: Leveraging field data to better understand the causes and consequences of infection and invasion in diverse systems". Huge congratulations to you both! We wish you luck on your next adventure.

CodeFest

The [Forest Carbon Codefest](#), hosted by Earth Lab and the Environmental Data Science Innovation & Inclusion Lab (ESILL), took place from March 12-14, 2024. At this event, six teams of 4-5 scientists (28 participants total) used open cyberinfrastructure and data to define original scientific questions that advance understanding of aboveground forest carbon dynamics as they relate to forest disturbance. Teams collaboratively addressed these questions using fully open and reproducible code script.

In collaboration with CU Boulder's Nature, Environment, Science & Technology (NEST) Studio for the Arts, the Codefest also hosted three artists during the event. These artists, after gaining inspiration and insight from the data and science, created artwork to inspire future Earth Lab and ESILL visitors. At the same time, they contributed their novel perspectives to the scientific work happening at the Codefest. Read more about each team's project on our event [webpage here](#).

By Tyler McIntosh

Team Social Events

In March, Earth Lab hosted a Spring Plant Swap. Team members repotted the office plants and brought seeds and seedlings to swap with colleagues. It was dirty, but rewarding work!

